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2 2023 and 2026 and was not accepted for publication (some were withdrawn due to APC). It
3 is deposited here as a record of the work and its findings. The study makes no claim to
4 mechanistic explanation; its value lies in mapping a question that has not previously been
5 addressed at this geographic and parametric scale. A list of submission attempts is appended
6 at the end of this document.

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8 **Global Climate Trends in Seven Climatic Parameters:**

9 **A Comparative Analysis Across 100 Locations**

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15 Short Title: Global climate trends in seven climatic parameters

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17 **HIGHLIGHTS**

- 18 ● Over 1984–2022, “climate change” as a globally uniform trend refers in practice to
19 temperature change alone.
- 20 ● Air temperature shows a consistent upward trend across almost all 100 globally
21 distributed locations over 1984–2022.
- 22 ● Earth temperature closely mirrors air temperature trends, confirming dataset reliability
23 ($R^2=0.897$).
- 24 ● Solar radiation, relative humidity, precipitation, wind speed, and temperature range
25 show no coherent global directional trend.
- 26 ● Rising temperature is the only climatic parameter warranting uniform design
27 guideline updates at a global scale.

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

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Much research and publicity focus on global temperature rise, but less attention has been given to whether other climatic parameters exhibit similarly universal trends. This study analyses linear trends in seven climatic parameters - air temperature, earth temperature, solar radiation, relative humidity, precipitation, wind speed, and air temperature range - across 100 globally distributed locations over the 39-year period 1984–2022, using publicly available NASA data. Trend slope coefficients were derived for each parameter at each location and compared pairwise through correlation analysis.

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Air and earth temperatures show a consistent upward trend across almost all locations, with the strong coupling between the two ($R^2=0.897$) confirming the reliability of the dataset. In contrast, solar radiation, relative humidity, precipitation, wind speed, and temperature range display no coherent global directional trend, with high variability between locations and no statistically meaningful global signal.

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These findings suggest that rising temperature is the only climatic parameter currently warranting uniform design guideline updates at a global scale. Other parameters remain locally variable and should be assessed on a location-specific basis rather than updated on the basis of global climate change assumptions.

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Keywords: Climate trends, Global analysis, Climatic parameters, Temperature rise, Climate change

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52 **1. Introduction**

53 While the increase in global mean air temperature is well established, the behaviour of related
54 parameters - solar radiation, humidity, precipitation, wind speed - over the same period and
55 across a comparable range of locations has received less systematic comparative attention.

56 Previous multi-parameter studies have made valuable contributions but typically cover limited
57 geographic ranges, restricted time periods, or focus on establishing average values rather than
58 trends. Jha et al. (2021) modelled future climate projections for India using precipitation,
59 temperature, and solar radiation data from 1980 to 2004. Lai and Dzombak (2019) examined
60 temperature and precipitation trends in the United States from the 19th century onward. The
61 global dataset compiled by New et al. (2002) covered eight climate elements across numerous
62 worldwide stations, but its objective was to establish climatological averages rather than to
63 assess directional trends (Figure 1). Lundstad et al. (2023) assembled an extensive historical
64 record spanning several centuries, but with uneven global distribution and measurement
65 discontinuities (Fig. 2). Adler et al. (2008, 2017) studied global precipitation anomalies and
66 trends, but without systematic comparison against other parameters. To the authors' knowledge,
67 no study has compared directional trends across a broad set of climatic parameters
68 simultaneously, across a globally distributed set of locations, over a continuous multi-decade
69 period.

70
71 *Figure 1. Distribution of stations for which mean temperature was available for the work of New et*
72 *al. (2002).*

73
74 *Figure 2. Distribution of locations included in the work of Lundstad et al. (2023).*

75 This study addresses that gap. It analyses linear trends in seven climatic parameters - air
76 temperature, earth temperature, solar radiation, relative humidity, precipitation, wind speed,
77 and air temperature range - across 100 globally distributed locations over the 39-year period
78 1984–2022. Trend slope coefficients were derived for each parameter at each location and
79 assessed through pairwise correlation analysis. The aim is to establish which parameters exhibit
80 globally consistent directional trends and which remain locally variable - a distinction with
81 direct relevance for urban planning, building design, and climate-responsive practice.

82 Data were drawn from the NASA POWER database, accessed via the RETScreen Expert
83 interface. The methodology is described in Section 2.

84 **2. Methodology**

85 A total of 100 locations worldwide were selected to achieve a broad geographic distribution
86 across continents, hemispheres, and climatic zones, without applying a formal sampling
87 protocol. Selection prioritised geographic spread while avoiding spatial clustering, resulting in
88 51 locations in the Northern Hemisphere and 49 in the Southern Hemisphere (Figure 3). Most
89 locations are urban centres of varying sizes, including coastal, inland, and high-altitude
90 settings. A small number of remote locations - such as Rapa Iti, Saint Helena, and the Antarctic
91 Mirny Station - were included specifically to extend coverage into areas without urban centres.
92 Full location details are provided in Table I.

93
94 *Figure 3. The 100 locations included in the study. Detailed information about each location can be*
95 *found in Table I.*

96 For each location, daily values of seven climatic parameters were extracted from the NASA
97 POWER database, accessed through the RETScreen Expert software interface, and averaged
98 to annual values for trend analysis. This yielded 39 annual values per parameter per location,
99 covering the period January 1984 to December 2022. RETScreen was the practical access point
100 when this study was initiated in 2017, as direct batch extraction through the NASA Data Access
101 Viewer was not yet available. It remains a convenient interface for this purpose today. The
102 parameters extracted were: mean, minimum, and maximum air temperature; relative humidity;
103 precipitation; horizontal solar radiation; wind speed; and earth temperature. Air temperature
104 range was calculated as the difference between annual minimum and maximum values.

105 For each parameter at each location, the 39-year mean was calculated and annual anomalies
106 determined as deviations from that mean. A least-squares linear regression was then applied to
107 the time series of annual anomalies, and the slope coefficient extracted as the primary analytical
108 variable. This slope represents the average annual rate of change of each parameter over the
109 study period, expressed in the unit of the parameter per year. A positive slope indicates an
110 increasing trend; a negative slope a decreasing trend. The resulting matrix of slope coefficients

111 - seven parameters across 100 locations - forms the dataset on which all subsequent analysis is
112 based. Pairwise correlations between parameter trends were assessed graphically through
113 scatter plots, with R^2 values reported for each comparison. The full slope coefficient dataset is
114 provided in Table III. In addition, Pearson correlation coefficients (r) were computed between
115 all pairs of parameter trend slopes, yielding a 9×9 correlation matrix (Table IV). Significance
116 stars indicate the p-value — the probability of observing a correlation of that magnitude by
117 chance if no real relationship existed (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$); white cells are not
118 statistically significant ($p \geq 0.05$).

119 **3. Results and Discussion**

120 The most striking pattern to emerge from this comprehensive pairwise analysis is its
121 asymmetry. One parameter - air temperature - shows a globally consistent upward trend across
122 almost all 100 locations, matched closely by earth temperature as expected from basic land-
123 atmosphere heat exchange principles. Every other parameter examined - solar radiation,
124 relative humidity, precipitation, wind speed, and temperature range - shows no coherent global
125 directional trend. These parameters increase in some locations and decrease in others, with
126 scatter that overwhelms any global signal. This asymmetry is the central finding of the study,
127 and it persists across all pairwise comparisons regardless of which parameter is placed on either
128 axis. The following sections document this pattern parameter by parameter.

129 *3.1 Air Temperature Compared To...*

130 *> Latitude (Figure 4):*

131 Almost all locations show positive warming slopes, confirming that rising air temperature is a
132 robust and consistent global trend over the study period. Warming rates are higher in the
133 northern hemisphere than in the southern hemisphere. Of the six exceptions that experience
134 cooling trends, four are located in the southern hemisphere. Cohen et al. (2014) and Estrada et
135 al. (2021) report comparable latitudinal patterns in global warming.

Figure 4. Air average temperature trends vs. latitude ($R^2=0.243$).

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138 Almost all locations are becoming more or less warm during the last four decades, especially
139 those on the northern hemisphere. The highest trends of temperature rise appear in Kishinev at
140 47.0° (point 18) and Norilsk (2), with the lowest drops in Mirny Station of Antarctica (99) and
141 Asuncion (77). Further research is needed to interpret the cooling trends at the six exceptions.

142 > *Solar radiation (Figure 5):*

143 Solar radiation is decreasing in 43 locations, even though their temperatures tend to rise.
144 Additionally, insolation is increasing in most of the few locations that are experiencing cooling.
145 The lack of a global relationship between insolation and temperature rise shown by the NASA
146 dataset corroborates that other factors are contributing to the warming phenomenon, rather than
147 solely the sun. This is a topic to investigate by considering additional parameters and larger-
148 scale phenomena. For example, in 25 of the 43 aforementioned locations, reduced insolation is
149 accompanied by increasing precipitation, which could indicate cloudiness. However, cloud
150 coverage or sunshine duration data are not included in the NASA dataset. The rise in relative
151 humidity observed in five of the remaining 18 less-sunny locations affects atmospheric
152 turbidity and could potentially explain the decrease in insolation. Further findings related to
153 insolation and its relationship with other variables are described below. The works of Wild et
154 al. (2016) and Prieto et al. (2009) among many others address the relation of solar radiation
155 and air temperature.

Figure 5. Radiation vs. air temperature ($R^2=0.011$).

Radiation trends are increasing in 57 locations (upper half), while temperature trends are rising in 40 locations despite their declining radiation trends (bottom right quarter). The highest radiation trends appear in warm and arid regions of the northern hemisphere: Amman (34) and Gadamis (37). Conversely, the lowest are found in mountainous locations of the south: Cuzco (66) and La Paz (68).

> *Relative humidity (Figure 6):*

Relative humidity trends show a decline in more than half of the locations, which aligns with the expected inverse relationship with temperature rise. Various local deviations may be explained by specific local conditions that require further investigation. Examples of research in this area are works by Willett et al. (2020), and Khalaf and Altmimi (2021).

Figure 6. Relative humidity vs. air temperature trends ($R^2=0.133$).

170 Across the 100 locations, RH trends span a comparatively narrow range. In 55 locations the
 171 RH trend is negative (bottom half), consistent with the drying effect of rising temperatures.
 172 The most pronounced drying appears in Brasilia (70) and Santiago (85), while the largest
 173 increases in RH occur in the high-altitude settings of Kabul (32) and La Paz (68), where
 174 warming trends are near zero or negative.

175 > *Precipitation (Figure 7):*

176 Precipitation trends increase as temperatures decrease, similar to relative humidity. Cooler
 177 conditions might be expected to promote both relative humidity and precipitation, yet this is
 178 not observed in 23 locations where the trends of the two parameters move in opposite
 179 directions. Relevant examples in the literature include Liang and Zhang (2021) and Wenxia et
 180 al. (2021).

181
 182 *Figure 7. Precipitation vs. air temperature trends ($R^2=0.042$).*

183 Increasing precipitation trends appear in 54 locations (top half), while 44 locations are warming
 184 up with lessening rainfall (bottom right). Manaus (54) and Diego Garcia (57) show the lowest
 185 precipitation trend, Manila (48) and Mumbai (44) the highest.

186 > *Air temperature ranges (Figure 8):*

187 Temperature range trends show no relationship with the direction or magnitude of warming:
 188 locations are almost equally split between widening and narrowing ranges. This confirms that
 189 the diurnal temperature range is governed primarily by local factors rather than by the global
 190 warming signal, and does not constitute a coherent global trend.

191
192 *Figure 8. Temperature range vs. air temperature trends ($R^2=0.010$).*

193 The temperature range trends are almost equally divided between increase and decrease (right
194 half). In both cases, the extreme range trends appear all in cold locations: Anchorage (7) and
195 Moscow (10) for the narrowest range, Magadan (9) and Irkutsk (11) for the widest.

196 *> Elevation from the sea (Figure 9):*

197 The graph reveals that the majority of the selected locations are situated below 500 meters
198 above sea level, with many located far from the coast. Warming trends appear to decrease as
199 elevation increases. An interesting question arises regarding the role of proximity to the sea in
200 this context. Bandopadhyay (2016) has studied this correlation in Bangladesh, as Thakuri et al.
201 (2019) in Nepal.

202
203 *Figure 9. Elevation vs. air temperature trends ($R^2=0$).*

204 The warming trends appear higher in low elevations above the sea level (bottom right). The
205 two locations at highest altitude, Lhasa (38) and Cuzco (66), are getting slightly warmer. The
206 minimum and maximum temperature trends, Mirny Station (99) and Kishinev (18) appear both

207 in low altitudes. The locations are not evenly selected per elevation, and that may affect the
 208 conclusions.

209 > *Climate zone (Figure 10):*

210 The lowest range of temperature trends is observed in the 'hot' zone 0, while the 'cool' zone 5
 211 exhibits the widest range, with both cooling and maximum warming trends. The blue trendline
 212 in the graph suggests higher warming trends as climates become cooler. Mahlstein et al. (2013)
 213 and Kim and Bae (2021) both used historical climate data to model future shifts in climate
 214 regions under warming conditions, at global and Asian scales respectively.

215
 216 *Figure 10. Climate zones vs. air temperature trends ($R^2=0.001$).*

217 The climate zones (ranging from '0-very hot' to '8-subarctic' per ASHRAE) seem to have a
 218 marginal average effect on the temperature rise trends. The highest temperature rises appear in
 219 zones 5 ('cool') and 8 ('subarctic/arctic') where Kishinev (18) and Norilsk (2) are. The locations
 220 in zone 0 ('very hot') have the narrowest range of temperature trends, those in zone 8 the widest
 221 including the lowest temperature trend (99).

222 > *Wind speed (Figure 11):*

223 Wind speed trends appear weakening in two-thirds of all locations. Rising wind speeds help
 224 moderate the temperature rise. The trendline indicates a slight decrease in wind speed as
 225 temperatures rise. The question here pertains to the cause-and-effect relationship between these
 226 two variables. Young and Ribal (2019) studied oceanic wind speed trends due to climate
 227 warming, while You et al. (2013) investigated the wind speed in Tibet after 1980.

Figure 11. Wind speed vs. air temperature trends ($R^2=0.005$).

Wind speed trends are rising in only 32 locations (top half of figure), while the remaining 68 show weakening or stable winds. Reduced wind speed accompanies warming at most locations, consistent with the slight negative trendline. The most extreme wind speed trends are found in the southern hemisphere: the largest decreases in Nairobi (53) and Auckland (89), the largest increases in Wellington (93) and the South Pole (100).

> *Earth temperature (Figure 12):*

Earth temperature follows the air temperature as expected. However, it is worth noting that out of the 90 locations with rising ground temperatures, 53 also experience increasing relative humidity and/or precipitation, which can influence the heat emitted from the ground due to the greenhouse effect of atmospheric vapour. This topic has been studied by Yang et al. (2022) with reference to China, while Hansen et al. (2010) analyse global data.

Figure 12. Earth temperature vs. air temperature trends ($R^2=0.897$).

243 In general, the earth temperature trends follow those of the air with some exceptions. The
 244 coldest earth temperature trends appear in cold Mirny Station (99) and Kabul (32), the warmest
 245 in Reunion (75) and Kishinev (18). The different trends of air and ground temperatures
 246 observed in several locations deserve further investigation.

247 *3.2 Radiation Compared To...*

248 *> Precipitation (Figure 13):*

249 The trends in precipitation provide insights into cloud coverage, which can affect solar
 250 radiation. It is observed that increasing precipitation trends correspond to decreasing insolation
 251 trends. However, there seems to be no significant impact of radiation on precipitation. The
 252 trendline illustrates an inverse relationship between the two variables. Díaz-Torres et al. (2017)
 253 have studied the relationship between rainfall and solar radiation. Similarly, Xue et al. (2023)
 254 have investigated this topic in China during the last millennium.

255
 256 *Figure 13. Radiation vs. precipitation trends ($R^2=0.027$).*

257 Precipitation is an indication of rainclouds that reduce insolation. The rise of radiation trends
 258 seems unaffected by precipitation (upper half). The higher precipitation trends appear to have
 259 a negative effect on the radiation as expected (right bottom). The locations with the minimum
 260 and maximum precipitation trends, Manaus (54) and Manila (48), present no change in
 261 radiation. The most extreme changes in radiation trends are in Amman (34) and Cuzco (66) but
 262 without any major change in precipitation.

263 *> Wind speed (Figure 14):*

264 The majority of locations experiencing increasing radiation trends also exhibit a decrease in
 265 wind speed. This tendency is also observed, to a lesser extent, in locations with declining

266 radiation trends. Sales dos Anjos et al. (2015) have analysed the correlations between these two
 267 variables in Brazil. Yazdani et al. (2016) have found that wind speed has little influence on
 268 solar radiation in Brunei; however, they do not mention if radiation affects the wind speed.

269
 270 *Figure 14. Radiation vs. wind speed ($R^2=0.007$).*

271 No clear global pattern emerges between radiation and wind speed trends. The largest cluster
 272 of locations combines increasing radiation with decreasing wind speed (top left), but the scatter
 273 is wide. Notably, Auckland (89) and Wellington (93) — both in New Zealand — show the
 274 most extreme wind speed trends in opposite directions, yet neither shows a notable change in
 275 radiation.

276 > *Earth temperature (Figure 15):*

277 The relationship between radiation and earth temperature trends appears similar to that with air
 278 temperature, as indicated by the trendline. Varonov and Shopov (2016) and Wang et al. (2013)
 279 have worked on this topic.

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Figure 15. Radiation vs. earth temperature trends ($R^2=0.007$).

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The rising insolation trends go along with the earth temperature trends in half of the locations (top right). However, in 40 other locations the earth temperature rises although the radiation is dropping (bottom right). Reunion (75) and Kishinev (18) have the highest earth temperature trend but with a limited radiation rise. The lowest earth temperature trends are in Mirny Station (99) and Kabul (32).

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> Relative humidity (Figure 16):

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When comparing relative humidity with radiation trends, it is evident that the two variables generally exhibit an inverse relationship in most locations, although there are some exceptions. This could be attributed to atmospheric turbidity, which is influenced by atmospheric vapour. The work of Wang et al. (2009), as well as the works of Wei et al. (2019) and Tasié et al. (2018) are in this area.

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Figure 16. Radiation vs. relative humidity trends ($R^2=0.027$).

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Radiation trends appear higher with reduced RH since the atmospheric vapour increases the atmospheric turbidity. In areas with lower insolation trends (bottom half), RH makes no difference. Kabul (32) has the highest rise of RH trends but with a negligible change in radiation trends. At the other end, Brasilia (70) presents the maximum reduction of RH together with some increase of insolation. On the top, Amman (34) that has the maximum increase in radiation is also slightly drier; at the bottom, Cuzco (66) has the maximum reduction in insolation terms with a minor increase of RH.

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> Latitude (Figure 17):

303 Most locations experiencing increasing radiation trends are located in the northern hemisphere,
 304 while the majority of locations with decreasing radiation trends are found in the southern
 305 hemisphere. Soler (1990) has explored the relation between latitude and solar radiation types
 306 seeking average values but not trends.

307
 308 *Figure 17. Radiation trends vs. latitude ($R^2=0.019$).*

309 Insolation trends increase more on the northern hemisphere (top right). The decrease is slightly
 310 stronger on the south (bottom left).

311 *3.3 Latitude Compared To...*

312 *> Relative humidity (Figure 18):*

313 The trends in relative humidity among different locations do not exhibit a clear pattern
 314 associated with latitude, as evidenced by the nearly horizontal trendline. However, it is worth
 315 noting that the increase in RH trends is more pronounced in the northern hemisphere compared
 316 to the southern hemisphere. The decrease trends are equal to both hemispheres. Peixoto and
 317 Oort (1996) are among those who have studied the variations of relative humidity across
 318 various latitudes, but not their trends.

Figure 18. Relative humidity trends vs. latitude ($R^2=0.009$).

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321 Overall, the effects of latitude on the RH trends appear negligible. The declining RH trends
 322 appear almost equally on both hemispheres (bottom half). The peak trend appears in Kabul
 323 (32) and the lowest in Brasilia (70).

324 > *Precipitation (Figure 19):*

325 Precipitation trends show an increasing pattern in the northern hemisphere and a decreasing
 326 pattern in the southern hemisphere. Notably, the positive and negative trends appear more
 327 pronounced near the equator than in regions closer to the poles. Adler et al. (2017) investigated
 328 planetary levels of precipitation linked with latitudes, while Zhang and Liang (2020) have
 329 studied precipitation in China based on latitude, longitude, and altitude.

Figure 19. Precipitation trends vs. latitude ($R^2=0.027$).

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332 Precipitation trends in northern latitudes appear rising (top right), in contrast with the declining
 333 trends of the southern hemisphere (bottom left). The maximum and minimum precipitation
 334 trends appear close to the equator, in Manila (48) and Manaus (54).

335 > *Wind speed (Figure 20):*

336 In most locations, wind speed trends are observed to be decreasing, particularly in the northern
 337 hemisphere, as indicated by the trendline. Conversely, the majority of locations experiencing
 338 increasing wind speeds are located in the southern hemisphere.

339
 340 *Figure 20. Wind speed trends vs. latitude ($R^2=0.036$).*

341 Wind speed trends drop in both hemispheres (bottom half), especially in the northern. The
 342 highest trend appears in Wellington (93), the lowest in Nairobi (53).

343 **3.4 Overall pattern**

344 Taken together, the pairwise comparisons tell a consistent story. Temperature - air and ground
 345 - is changing directionally and globally. The remaining parameters are not, at least not in any
 346 globally uniform sense. Their trends are real at the local level but cancel out across locations,
 347 producing near-zero global correlations in every pairwise comparison. This asymmetry is the
 348 central finding of the study. The Pearson correlation matrix (Table IV) makes it visible
 349 numerically: the air-earth temperature pair yields $r=+0.947$ ($p<0.001$), while every other cross-
 350 parameter pair either falls below $r=\pm 0.30$ or is not statistically significant. Of 36 possible pairs,
 351 22 show no significant correlation.

352 **4. Implications**

353 This study examined linear trends in seven climatic parameters across 100 globally distributed
 354 locations over the 39-year period 1984–2022. The central finding is asymmetrical: air

355 temperature (and closely coupled earth temperature) shows a consistent upward trend across
356 almost all locations, whereas solar radiation, relative humidity, precipitation, wind speed, and
357 air temperature range exhibit no coherent global directional signal. Their trends vary widely by
358 location, with increases in some places balancing decreases in others.

359 *4.1 Implications for design and planning practice*

360 For professionals in building design, urban planning, and infrastructure engineering, this
361 distinction carries practical weight. Many design standards and guidelines (e.g., for heating and
362 cooling loads, facade performance, outdoor thermal comfort) rely on climate data that are
363 periodically updated to reflect changing conditions. The results suggest that:

- 364 • Temperature-dependent parameters (cooling degree-days, outdoor design temperatures,
365 urban heat island mitigation) should be updated with the expectation of continued warming
366 globally. The magnitude of adjustment will be location-specific, but the direction is
367 universally upward.
- 368 • Parameters such as solar radiation, humidity, precipitation, and wind should not be treated
369 as if they follow a uniform global trend. Instead, design assumptions for these variables
370 must be based on local or regional trend analyses, because a global average would obscure
371 opposite regional changes. For example, a decrease in wind speed in one region and an
372 increase in another both matter locally, but neither justifies a global design rule.

373 Thus, “climate change” as a design driver should be disaggregated: temperature is a globally
374 coherent variable, while other climatic parameters are location-dependent and require
375 case-by-case assessment.

376 *4.2 Implications for climate science and monitoring*

377 The asymmetry also has implications for how climate trends are communicated and studied.
378 The strong coupling between air and earth temperature trends ($R^2 = 0.897$) reinforces the
379 reliability of the NASA POWER dataset for long-term land-surface analysis. More
380 importantly, the absence of a global trend in non-temperature variables is itself an informative
381 result. It aligns with physical expectations: precipitation, wind, and humidity are more strongly
382 governed by regional circulation patterns, land-surface feedbacks, and decadal oscillations,
383 which can cause trends to vary in sign across the globe. The analysis shows that over the past
384 four decades, these variations have not coalesced into a globally uniform signal.

385 For climate monitoring, this underscores the value of network-based, local-trend assessments
386 rather than reliance on global averages. Even when a global average for precipitation or wind
387 speed shows little net change, local trends can be substantial and of high societal relevance.
388 Future work should therefore focus on regional trend detection and attribution, as well as on
389 understanding the drivers of the observed spatial variability.

390 *4.3 Implications for standards and policy*

391 Organisations that maintain climatic design standards (e.g., ASHRAE, CIBSE, national
392 building codes) periodically revise the underlying climate data. The findings suggest that:

- 393 • Temperature-related clauses should be updated globally, using the best available
394 projections and trend data.
- 395 • Non-temperature clauses (e.g., solar radiation for photovoltaic sizing, wind loads,
396 precipitation intensity for drainage design) should be updated using region-specific trend
397 analyses or, where trends are not statistically significant, maintained as stationary variables
398 with appropriate safety margins. A blanket global update for these parameters would not
399 be justified by the evidence.

400 **5 Limitations and future research**

401 The 100 locations were not selected through a formal sampling protocol and are predominantly
402 urban, which raises the question of whether temperature trends are inflated by Urban Heat
403 Island (UHI) effects. To assess this, temperature trend slopes were plotted against city
404 population as a proxy for urbanisation intensity (Figure 21). The relationship is essentially
405 absent ($R^2 = 0.001$): cities with populations in the tens of millions warm at rates
406 indistinguishable from small towns, and several of the strongest warming signals occur at
407 locations with near-zero populations (e.g., Mirny Station, Rapa Iti). This indicates that UHI is
408 not a systematic driver of the observed temperature trends in this dataset. A more rigorous test
409 - using paired urban–rural comparisons at the same locations - remains a valuable direction
410 for future work.

Figure 21. Air temperature trends vs. population ($R^2=0.001$).

Beyond the urbanisation question, the analysis relies on linear trend models over a 39-year period, which may not capture non-linear changes or multi-decadal variability. The dataset covers only land-based locations; oceanic trends may differ. No formal significance testing was applied to individual trend slopes, and the spatial distribution of the 100 sites, while broad, is not statistically representative of the global land surface.

Future research should therefore:

- Although Figure 21 suggests UHI is not a systematic driver at the global scale, urban–rural paired stations at the same locations could be used to confirm this finding at the local level.
- Apply significance testing to individual slopes and assess the proportion of locations where trends are statistically distinguishable from zero.
- Use non-linear trend methods and assess changes in variability alongside mean trends.
- Extend the analysis to longer periods and include satellite-based ocean data.
- Investigate the physical drivers behind contrasting regional trends in non-temperature parameters.

Within the limits of this study, the key message remains: among the climatic parameters most relevant to built environment practice, temperature is the only one that exhibits a consistent, global directional trend. The other parameters do not - they change in place-specific ways that cannot be captured by a global narrative of uniform climate change. Recognising this asymmetry is essential for scientifically grounded adaptation and design.

434 5.1 *Research agenda*

435 The correlation matrix (Table IV) and the pairwise comparisons raise a number of specific
436 questions that the present study opens but does not attempt to answer due to the substantial
437 extent of the topic. Each represents a tractable research programme in its own right:

- 438 • Why does solar radiation show no globally coherent trend despite near-universal warming
439 (Figure 5)? Is the signal masked by opposing regional dynamics — such as the cloud-cover
440 and humidity effects noted in section 3.1 — or is the 39-year period insufficient to reveal
441 it?
- 442 • Why do wind speed trends weaken in two-thirds of locations but strengthen in the southern
443 hemisphere? What role do large-scale circulation changes play, and does the pattern persist
444 over longer periods?
- 445 • Why does precipitation increase in the northern hemisphere and decrease in the southern
446 hemisphere at low latitudes? Is this a manifestation of the inter-tropical convergence zone
447 shift documented elsewhere?
- 448 • What physical mechanisms explain the locations where air and earth temperature trends
449 diverge most sharply (Figures 12, 15)? For continental arid locations such as Kabul (32),
450 soil moisture depletion, land use change, or large-scale irrigation are plausible contributors.
451 For island locations such as Réunion (75), the divergence is more likely related to oceanic
452 influence and orographic effects across a small land area.

453 The scope of this study was a deliberate design choice, not a limitation. Its value lies precisely
454 in opening questions for further research in depth rather than exhausting them.

455 **Author contributions**

456 **Thanos N. Stasinopoulos:** conceptualization, methodology, data curation, software
457 development, analysis, writing (original draft, review and editing), project administration. The
458 author has read and agreed to the published version of the paper.

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464 accessed through the RETScreen Expert interface at [http://www.nrcan.gc.ca/energy/software-](http://www.nrcan.gc.ca/energy/software-tools/7465)
465 [tools/7465](http://www.nrcan.gc.ca/energy/software-tools/7465).

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583 **TABLES**

584 *Table I. The 100 locations of the study. Data from National Centers for Environmental*
 585 *Information; population from United Nations (2024).*

	Reference Code	Location name	Country code ISO 3166-1	Latitude °	Longitude °	Elevation m	Climate Zone	Population
1	CMJ	Cape Morris Jesu	GRL	83.7	-33.4	4	8	0
2	NOR	Norilsk	RUS	69.3	88.2	232	8	176,000
3	ARK	Arkhangelsk	RUS	64.6	40.6	4	7	348,000
4	REY	Reykjavik	ISL	64.1	-21.9	61	6A	240,000
5	IQA	Iqaluit	CAN	63.8	-68.6	34	8	7,200
6	TRO	Trondheim	NOR	63.5	10.9	17	6A	190,000
7	ANC	Anchorage	USA	61.3	-149.6	115	7	290,000
8	OSL	Oslo	NOR	59.9	106.0	17	6A	700,000
9	MAG	Magadan	RUS	59.5	150.8	116	8	90,000
10	MOS	Moscow	RUS	55.8	37.6	156	6A	12.7 M
11	IRK	Irkutsk	RUS	52.3	104.3	469	7	620,000
12	LON	London	GBR	51.5	-0.1	43	4A	9 M
13	AST	Astana	KAZ	51.1	71.4	350	7	1.2 M
14	WIN	Winnipeg	CAN	49.9	-92.7	239	7	750,000
15	VAN	Vancouver	CAN	49.3	-123.1	3	4C	2.6 M
16	MUN	Munich	DEU	48.1	11.6	520	5A	1.5 M
17	BAS	Basel	CHE	47.5	7.6	316	5A	177,000
18	KIV	Kishinev	MDA	47.0	29.0	173	5A	700,000
19	URU	Urumqi	CHN	43.8	87.7	947	6B	3.5 M
20	AND	Andorra	AND	42.5	1.5	1217	5A	22,000
21	BOS	Boston	USA	42.4	-71.0	9	4A	4.8 M
22	NAP	Naples	ITA	40.8	14.3	72	4A	1.0 M
23	BAK	Baku	AZE	40.4	49.9	43	4B	2.2 M
24	ANK	Ankara	TUR	40.0	32.7	806	4A	5.2 M
25	BEI	Beijing	CHN	39.9	116.3	55	4B	21.0 M
26	DEN	Denver	USA	39.6	-104.8	1793	5A	750,000
27	AZO	Azores	PRT	38.5	-28.7	41	3A	68,000

28	IZM	Izmir	TUR	38.3	27.1	120	3A	4.3 M
29	ATH	Athens	GRC	37.9	23.7	15	3A	3.1 M
30	RHO	Rhodes	GRC	36.4	28.1	11	3A	50,000
31	TOK	Tokyo	JPN	35.8	139.4	139	4A	37.0 M
32	KAB	Kabul	AFG	34.5	69.2	2382	5C	4.4 M
33	BEY	Beirut	LBN	33.8	35.5	19	2A	2.0 M
34	AMM	Amman	JOR	32.0	36.0	779	3B	400,000
35	MAR	Marrakesh	MAR	31.6	-8.0	466	2B	1.0 M
36	CAI	Cairo	EGY	30.1	31.4	74	2B	20.0 M
37	GAD	Ghadames	LYB	30.1	9.5	363	2B	10,000
38	LHA	Lhasa	CHN	29.7	91.1	3650	5C	210,000
39	RIY	Riyadh	SAU	24.7	45.7	620	1B	7.6 M
40	HAV	Havana	CUB	23.0	-82.4	75	1A	2.1 M
41	HOK	Hong Kong	HKG	22.3	114.2	62	2A	7.4 M
42	HON	Honolulu	USA	21.3	-157.9	5	1B	350,000
43	MEX	Mexico City	MEX	19.4	-99.1	2235	3C	22.0 M
44	MUM	Mumbai	IND	19.1	72.8	14	0A	20.0 M
45	BIL	Bilma	NER	18.7	12.9	442	0B	5,000
46	KHA	Khartoum	SDN	15.7	32.5	380	0B	5.3 M
47	CAV	Cape Verde	CPV	15.1	-23.5	20	1B	160,000
48	MNL	Manila	PHL	14.6	121.0	13	0A	13.0 M
49	BAN	Bangkok	THA	13.7	100.6	4	0A	9.5 M
50	KOL	Kolkata	IND	13.0	80.2	16	0A	14.0 M
51	LAG	Lagos	NGA	6.4	3.5	12	0A	15.0 M
52	BOG	Bogota	COL	4.7	-74.1	2546	3C	8.0 M
53	NAI	Nairobi	KEN	-1.3	36.9	1624	3A	4.5 M
54	MAN	Manaus	BRA	-2.8	-59.6	70	1A	2.2 M
55	KIN	Kinshasa	COD	-4.3	15.3	1358	1A	150 M
56	JAK	Jakarta	IDN	-6.3	106.8	8	0A	34.0 M
57	DIE	Diego Garcia	IOT	-7.3	72.4	3	0A	0
58	REC	Recife	BRA	-8.1	-34.8	19	0A	1.6 M
59	BAL	Bali	IDN	-8.8	115.2	1	0A	900,000
60	LUA	Luanda	AGO	-8.9	13.0	70	1B	9.2 M
61	TIM	Timor	IDN	-9.1	124.0	272	1A	277,000
62	POM	Port Moresby	PNG	-9.5	147.2	28	0A	400,000
63	LUB	Lubumbashi	COD	-11.6	27.5	1260	2A	1.8 M
64	LIM	Lima	PER	-12.0	-77.1	13	2B	10.0 M
65	DAR	Darwin	AUS	-12.4	130.9	30	0A	150,000
66	CUZ	Cuzco	PER	-13.5	-71.9	3249	4C	430,000
67	SAM	Samoa	WSM	-13.9	-172.0	57	0A	37,000
68	LAP	La Paz	BOL	-15.3	-68.2	1744	3A	850,000
69	LUS	Lusaka	ZMB	-15.4	28.3	1154	2A	3.0 M
70	BRA	Brasilia	BRA	-15.8	-47.9	1159	2A	4.7 M
71	FJI	Fiji	FJI	-17.1	176.9	5	0A	94,000
72	HAR	Harare	ZWE	-17.8	31.0	1472	3A	2.0 M
73	ANT	Antananarivo	MDG	-18.8	47.5	1276	3A	1.4 M

74	COO	Cook Islands	COK	-18.8	-159.8	4	1A	17,000
75	REU	Reunion	REU	-21.3	55.5	127	1A	150,000
76	ALI	Alice Springs	AUS	-23.8	133.9	547	2B	25,000
77	ASU	Asuncion	PRY	-25.3	-57.5	101	2A	525,000
78	JOH	Johannesburg	ZAF	-26.3	27.8	1507	3A	9.4 M
79	PAS	Pascua Island	CHL	-27.2	-109.4	69	2A	0
80	BRI	Brisbane	AUS	-27.4	153.1	10	2A	2.5 M
81	RAP	Rapa Iti	PYF	-27.6	-144.3	2	2A	500
82	DUR	Durban	ZAF	-30.0	31.0	14	2A	1.2 M
83	POA	Porto Alegre	BRA	-30.0	-52.2	47	3A	1.5 M
84	PER	Perth	AUS	-31.9	115.9	25	3A	2.2 M
85	SAN	Santiago	CHL	-33.5	-70.7	520	3C	6.3 M
86	SYD	Sydney	AUS	-33.8	151.2	40	3A	5.4 M
87	CAP	Cape Town	ZAF	-34.0	18.6	42	3C	4.6 M
88	BUE	Buenos Ayres	ARG	-34.8	-58.5	20	4A	15.0 M
89	AUC	Auckland	NZL	-37.0	174.8	7	4A	1.7 M
90	SHE	Saint Helena	SHN	-37.1	-12.3	7	4A	4,500
91	AMI	Amsterdam Island	ATF	-37.8	77.5	29	4A	0
92	MEL	Melbourne	AUS	-37.8	145.0	32	4A	5.0 M
93	WEL	Wellington	NZL	-41.3	174.8	127	4A	215,000
94	HOB	Hobart	AUS	-42.9	147.3	51	4A	60,000
95	INV	Invercargill	NZL	-46.4	168.3	2	4A	57,000
96	PAF	Port-aux-Français	ATF	-49.3	70.2	30	6A	1,000
97	FAL	Falklands	FLK	-51.6	-59.5	47	6A	3,400
98	PUN	Punta Arenas	CHL	-53.0	-71.0	37	6A	130,000
99	MIR	Mirny Station	ATA	-66.5	93.0	30	8	0
100	SOU	South Pole	ATA	-90.0	0.0	2835	8	0

586 *Table II. Exemplary table showing data of Amman as used in this study (location 34). The*
587 *columns on the right show the annual anomalies of the corresponding values on the left*
588 *compared with the averages shown at the bottom left row ("average"). The values at bottom*
589 *right row ("slope") refer to a linear regression line per each parameter anomaly. These slope*
590 *values are used in the graphs shown in Figure 4 to Figure 20.*

	Annual averages									Annual anomalies								
	Air temperature - average (°C)	Air temperature - minimum (°C)	Air temperature - maximum (°C)	Relative humidity (%)	Precipitation (mm)	Daily solar radiation - horizontal	Wind speed (m/s)	Earth temperature (°C)	Temperature range (°C)	Air temperature average anomaly (°C)	Air temperature - min. anomaly (°C)	Air temperature - max. anomaly (°C)	Relative humidity anomaly (%)	Precipitation anomaly (mm)	Daily solar radiation - horizontal anomaly	Wind speed anomaly (m/s)	Earth temperature anomaly (°C)	Temperature range anomaly (°C)
1984	20.3	1.3	41.1	57	283	4.85	3.0	21.0	39.9	-0.7	0.7	-3.0	0.5	15.2	-0.6	-0.1	-0.9	-3.7
1985	20.7	-1.6	45.6	55	257	4.81	3.1	21.6	47.2	-0.2	-2.1	1.5	-1.1	-10.7	-0.6	0.0	-0.4	3.7
1986	20.4	1.0	43.1	59	360	4.86	3.1	21.2	42.0	-0.6	0.4	-1.1	2.0	91.6	-0.6	0.0	-0.8	-1.5
1987	20.6	2.7	44.5	57	228	4.80	3.2	21.5	41.8	-0.4	2.1	0.4	0.7	-39.6	-0.6	0.1	-0.5	-1.7
1988	20.7	1.1	43.1	57	362	4.76	3.1	21.6	42.0	-0.3	0.5	-1.0	0.6	94.1	-0.7	0.0	-0.4	-1.5
1989	20.5	-3.3	42.8	56	164	5.01	2.8	21.4	46.1	-0.5	-3.8	-1.3	-1.1	-104.2	-0.4	-0.2	-0.5	2.6
1990	20.5	-0.7	42.4	55	241	5.01	3.0	21.5	43.1	-0.5	-1.3	-1.7	-1.4	-26.8	-0.4	0.0	-0.5	-0.4
1991	20.3	-0.1	41.6	58	434	4.82	3.0	21.2	41.7	-0.7	-0.7	-2.5	1.6	165.4	-0.6	0.0	-0.7	-1.8
1992	19.0	-2.2	43.2	60	424	4.96	3.0	19.7	45.4	-2.0	-2.8	-0.9	3.3	156.0	-0.4	0.0	-2.3	1.8

1993	20.3	-1.7	44.2	56	176	5.00	2.9	21.2	46.0		-0.6	-2.3	0.1	-1.0	-92.1	-0.4	-0.1	-0.8	2.4
1994	20.9	1.0	43.3	58	409	4.98	3.1	21.8	42.3		-0.1	0.4	-0.8	1.0	141.4	-0.4	0.1	-0.1	-1.2
1995	20.3	2.8	42.8	58	148	5.12	2.9	21.2	40.0		-0.7	2.2	-1.3	1.4	-119.9	-0.3	-0.1	-0.8	-3.5
1996	20.9	2.5	44.1	58	255	5.00	3.1	21.8	41.6		-0.1	1.9	0.0	1.3	-13.5	-0.4	0.0	-0.1	-1.9
1997	20.2	-1.9	42.8	59	363	5.17	3.0	21.0	44.7		-0.8	-2.4	-1.3	2.4	94.5	-0.2	0.0	-0.9	1.2
1998	21.3	2.2	45.9	57	242	5.30	3.0	22.3	43.7		0.3	1.6	1.8	0.7	-26.2	-0.1	0.0	0.4	0.2
1999	21.4	2.9	43.1	54	138	5.24	3.0	22.5	40.2		0.4	2.3	-1.0	-2.5	-130.0	-0.2	0.0	0.6	-3.3
2000	20.5	1.2	47.4	58	297	5.32	3.0	21.6	46.2		-0.5	0.6	3.3	1.2	29.4	-0.1	0.0	-0.4	2.7
2001	21.3	0.6	43.6	57	268	5.87	3.0	22.3	43.0		0.3	0.0	-0.5	0.7	-0.3	0.5	-0.1	0.4	-0.5
2002	20.9	0.7	45.5	58	358	5.75	3.2	21.8	44.8		-0.1	0.1	1.4	1.1	90.2	0.3	0.2	-0.1	1.3
2003	20.8	3.3	42.9	59	397	5.68	3.2	21.6	39.6		-0.2	2.7	-1.2	2.7	128.6	0.3	0.1	-0.3	-3.9
2004	20.9	-1.6	43.9	57	283	5.75	3.0	21.9	45.5		-0.1	-2.2	-0.2	0.1	14.8	0.3	0.0	-0.1	2.0
2005	20.8	1.8	42.6	56	270	5.74	3.1	21.8	40.8		-0.1	1.2	-1.5	-0.9	1.7	0.3	0.1	-0.2	-2.7
2006	20.7	1.2	43.1	56	248	5.70	3.0	21.7	42.0		-0.3	0.6	-1.0	-0.8	-20.1	0.3	-0.1	-0.2	-1.6
2007	21.1	2.2	47.5	57	274	5.70	3.0	22.2	45.3		0.1	1.6	3.4	0.8	5.8	0.3	-0.1	0.2	1.8
2008	21.4	-2.5	42.9	53	212	5.78	3.1	22.4	45.4		0.4	-3.1	-1.2	-3.4	-56.3	0.4	0.0	0.5	1.9
2009	21.1	0.6	42.5	57	320	5.71	3.1	22.0	41.9		0.1	0.0	-1.6	0.2	52.2	0.3	0.0	0.1	-1.6
2010	22.7	1.6	47.5	52	231	5.73	3.1	23.7	46.0		1.7	1.0	3.4	-4.2	-37.4	0.3	0.0	1.7	2.4
2011	20.4	2.2	44.7	59	287	5.68	3.0	21.4	42.4		-0.6	1.7	0.5	2.0	19.0	0.3	-0.1	-0.6	-1.1
2012	21.3	0.7	46.6	58	333	5.61	3.0	22.2	45.9		0.3	0.1	2.5	1.0	65.0	0.2	0.0	0.3	2.4
2013	21.0	0.4	41.5	57	307	5.72	3.2	21.9	41.1		0.0	-0.2	-2.6	0.1	39.4	0.3	0.1	0.0	-2.4
2014	21.4	0.6	44.2	56	237	5.78	3.0	22.4	43.5		0.5	0.0	0.0	-0.8	-30.8	0.4	-0.1	0.4	0.0
2015	21.4	-1.8	46.3	56	197	5.66	3.1	22.4	48.1		0.4	-2.4	2.2	-0.4	-71.2	0.2	0.1	0.4	4.5
2016	21.8	-2.4	44.1	54	234	5.75	3.1	22.9	46.5		0.8	-3.0	-0.1	-2.6	-33.8	0.3	0.1	1.0	2.9
2017	21.6	0.2	45.1	53	92	5.77	3.0	22.8	44.9		0.6	-0.4	0.9	-3.4	-176.1	0.4	-0.1	0.8	1.4
2018	22.3	4.9	44.4	56	243	5.63	3.0	23.4	39.4		1.3	4.3	0.2	-0.1	-24.9	0.2	0.0	1.4	-4.1
2019	21.4	2.3	44.0	56	255	5.76	3.2	22.4	41.7		0.4	1.7	-0.1	-0.7	-13.3	0.4	0.1	0.4	-1.8
2020	21.7	1.0	47.1	59	259	5.65	3.1	22.8	46.1		0.7	0.4	3.0	2.6	-9.4	0.2	0.1	0.9	2.6
2021	22.2	1.3	43.5	54	183	5.85	3.1	23.3	42.2		1.2	0.7	-0.6	-2.8	-85.5	0.4	0.1	1.4	-1.3
2022	21.6	-1.6	45.8	56	186	5.70	3.0	22.8	47.3		0.6	-2.1	1.6	-0.5	-81.9	0.3	-0.1	0.8	3.8

average: 21.0 0.6 44.1 57 268 5.41 3.1 22.0 43.5 slope: 0.043 0.016 0.056 -0.05 -2.18 0.030 0.001 0.050 0.039

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Table III. R^2 values of the trendlines.

Figure 4: 0.243	Figure 10: 0.001	Figure 16: 0.027
Figure 5: 0.011	Figure 11: 0.005	Figure 17: 0.019
Figure 6: 0.133	Figure 12: 0.897	Figure 18: 0.009
Figure 7: 0.042	Figure 13: 0.027	Figure 19: 0.027
Figure 8: 0.010	Figure 14: 0.007	Figure 20: 0.036
Figure 9: 0.000	Figure 15: 0.007	Figure 21: 0.001

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Table IV. Pearson correlation matrix of annual trend slopes across 100 locations ($n=100$). Each cell shows the correlation coefficient r between the linear trend slopes of two climatic parameters across all 100 locations. Strong positive correlations appear in blue, strong negative correlations in red, and cells where the correlation is not statistically significant ($p \geq 0.05$) in white. Asterisks denote significance level: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

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The dominant feature is the near-perfect correlation between air and earth temperature trends ($r = +0.947$), while all other parameter pairs show weak or non-significant relationships, confirming the asymmetry identified in the pairwise scatter plots.

	T air	T min	T max	RH	Precip	Solar rad	Wind	T earth	T range
T air	1	+0.538***	+0.544***	-0.360***	-0.201*	+0.115	-0.054	+0.947***	-0.082
T min	+0.538***	1	+0.263**	-0.227*	-0.096	-0.156	-0.010	+0.564***	-0.704***
T max	+0.544***	+0.263**	1	-0.513***	-0.354***	+0.086	+0.118	+0.533***	+0.501***
RH	-0.360***	-0.227*	-0.513***	1	+0.584***	-0.155	-0.092	-0.425***	-0.174
Precip	-0.201*	-0.096	-0.354***	+0.584***	1	-0.162	-0.173	-0.281**	-0.175
Solar rad	+0.115	-0.156	+0.086	-0.155	-0.162	1	-0.079	+0.094	+0.203*
Wind	-0.054	-0.010	+0.118	-0.092	-0.173	-0.079	1	+0.015	+0.096
T earth	+0.947***	+0.564***	+0.533***	-0.425***	-0.281**	+0.094	+0.015	1	-0.114
T range	-0.082	-0.704***	+0.501***	-0.174	-0.175	+0.203*	+0.096	-0.114	1

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